

The Essence of Freedom in Jean-Paul Sartre: Implications for the Nigerian Society

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Abstract

This work examines Jean-Paul Sartre's theory of freedom, arguing that existence precedes essence in the pursuit of freedom. While authentic choice grants the individual the potency to realise his or her potentials in the world, the conceptual and contextual analysis maintains that existence precedes essence, signifying that man's essence is not immanent prior to existence, since he is not pre-determined or pre-defined by any destiny. Man is condemned to be free, meaning that he bears full responsibility for his choices within the limits of his situation. Authentic living and radical choice-making are fundamental features that define human consciousness in responding to actions and circumstances. The work contends that unless individuals struggle to liberate themselves and society through the responsible exercise of radical freedom, they risk remaining bound to circumstances characterised by bad faith. Bad faith represents self-deception, evasion of responsibility, procrastination, indecisiveness, and other forms of stagnation that hinder human access to freedom and progress. The research argues that radical freedom is a genuine path to self-realisation, provoking being-in-the-world to make deliberate and transformative choices. In the struggle for freedom, man must choose either to affirm his freedom or to deny it. Sartre distinguishes being-for-itself as a conscious being capable of reflective awareness and decisive action, whereas being-in-itself refers to an unconscious and non-reflective mode of being. The work concludes that freedom is fundamental and indispensable, serving as the primary condition through which human beings create meaning and define their existence.

Keywords: Freedom, Consciousness, Bad Faith, Being-For-Itself, Being-In-Itself, Essence, Existence.

Introduction

This work evaluates the essence of freedom in the face of human existence. It deeply captures humans as the centre of the universe. Sartre is of the opinion that existence precedes essence which implies that human existence is considered first before its essence. The study entails that man was born without pre-determined and pre-defined nature that is to say that his destiny is in his hand, he is responsible for his actions, success and backwardness, neither God/god nor fate can be blamed or appraised. Therefore, man must struggle to create essence and whatness to their existence through absolute freedom. He further claimed that 'man is condemned to be free' meaning man is the master of his freedom and has all it takes to choose and accomplish what he wishes. 'Condemned to be free' gives humans the key to radical choice and authentic life to make man create what he wishes in life. Facticity is an inherent nature in the history of human existence and man should by all means refrain from being hindered by it. Individuals are considered as possessors of their possessions considering the fact that their freedom knows no limit in the world of existence. Humans must know without equivocation that nature did not prepare any blueprint, luck, or design for any individual. Therefore, whatever success one achieves is strictly for his choice and ability. Notwithstanding, consciousness and authenticity are considered as the key components that give motion and potency to the being-in-the-world.

The paper views freedom as an indispensable value that gives humans free access to assess or reject the world for reason best known to them. In the state of anguish, man is already aware of the anxiety and responsibility attached to the possession of freedom. But having authenticity as the key factor dowses the tension. Living cowardly and below standard is living in bad faith and living in bad faith is living in self-deception and unauthentic life which likely reduces being-for-itself to being-in-itself.

Furthermore, the work clearly describes freedom as limitless and boundless world of liberty where humans reserve authentic choice either to choose to die or choose to live on course of protecting themselves or their country. Disability and one's background are imperatively not limitation to freedom rather your concept; you decide how to define and live with them by choice. Freedom is hereby extended to sociopolitical society where self-realised persons sacrifice their time and efforts to bring sanity, order and milestone development to the country. The work concludes that before the society moves forward, individuals must be purged of their mental constraints and mental slavery emanating from bad faith. On this note, individuals are charged to opt for active freedom so that the society will be freely run by those whose minds are already trained and examined for leadership.

Explication of Terms

'Existence' is used to address all existing beings and their characteristics, 'essence' implies the purpose and meaning of all living beings, 'consciousness' is the power of the mind and awareness toward achieving a particular goal, 'transcendence' connotes rising beyond the physical realm, 'facticity' refers to facts of man's unchangeability in existence, such as his birth, past experience, and social condition. 'Bad faith' implies a state of self-deception especially in a situation where one denies themselves the basic freedom and sense of responsibility by acting in a manner that they are determined in something else than accepting their full conscious being. 'Being-for-itself' represents conscious beings while 'being-in-itself' indicates unconscious beings. 'Nothingness' here does not imply absence of something but a central active force to human consciousness and freedom for self-creativity.

The Oxford online University Press defines freedom as the state or fact of being free from servitude, constraint, inhibition and liberty.¹ In ancient philosophy freedom was described in

different perspectives such as; being differentiated from slavery or tyranny a situation where individuals were subject under the arbitrary will of others for instance, the concept of freedom or liberty in the Roman empire emphasized both personal freedom and the collective freedom of the Roman people from oppressive rule².

Socrates posits that true freedom is synonymous to virtue as well applicable to examined life guided by reason. Aristotle connected freedom to living in a just and virtuous society within the city-state. Sophists affirmed that man can achieve freedom by liberating himself and disintegrating himself from mental and social constraints, venturing into difficult tasks and focusing towards higher creativity. Thus, said sophists, “the idea of inner freedom suggests that individuals could be free even in the face of external constraints.”⁴ Epictetus considered distinguishing what is within our capacities such as thoughts, creativity and actions. Then what is not within us, like external things. Epictetus was simply trying to differentiate between self-slavery and external slavery caused by constraints already existing before the existence of man such as birth, location and existence itself. While Romans had combined notions that freedom and liberty are both personal and political. More so lying emphasis on the protection of individual rights and overall freedom of the Roman citizens.

The concept of freedom in modern philosophy is classical, autonomous, and multifaceted in nature. Individuals possess the autonomy, to drive to any length and to actualise their dreams for freedom. Freedom and liberty are synonymously working in alliance to achieving similar goal. Freedom in political context concentrates on the right and liberties of the citizens under the umbrella of political system. It involves freedom of speech, fundamental human rights and other civic requirements.

The Theory of Being and Existence in the World.

Both living and non-living are regarded as being in the context. Existence implies the physical appearance of beings in the material world. Sartre has two main types of being in the world, the conscious and the unconscious beings. Being-for-itself is the being that possesses consciousness while being-in-itself is a being that lacks consciousness. Being-in-the-world is known as anthropocentrism the imperative that man is the centre of the universe.

In the theory of existentialism, Sartre posited that ‘being-for-itself’ is condemned to be free because it is conscious and aware of the self. A being that possesses consciousness and choice is capable of choosing whatever they wish in the world. There is no pre-determined objective that nature offers to a man in dispense of his existence. In that regard, man is charged to struggle to make his ends meet. Existence precedes and commands essence according to Sartre. Freedom makes itself an act, and we ordinarily attain it across that act which it organises with the causes, motives and ends which the act implies (Sartre, 1943, p. 438)

The Concept of Freedom

Sartre conceptualised freedom as the ability of individuals to conquer their mental constraints and embrace radical choice. He believed that nature did not prepare any luxury, success and future for any person rather all existing and meaningful individuals must rise to face their challenges and win themselves successes. Sartre shared similar thought with Martin Heidegger that man was “thrown” into the world without fixed plans which justifies his popular saying that ‘man is condemned to be free’. To be free is a choice and by authentic choice and consciousness man can choose to be free. According to him “freedom is the freedom of choosing but not freedom of not

choosing, not to choose is, in fact, to choose not to choose⁷(Sartre 1943, p. 481). Sartre meant that freedom is all about choice making, choosing not to be free is choosing on its own. In his book *Being and Nothingness*, he quoted Gottfried Leibniz for saying that: freedom by human reality is organisation of three different notions: 1, man is free to determine himself rationally to perform an act. 2, That such act is understood fully by the very nature of the one who has committed it. 3, It is contingent – that is, it exists in such a way that other persons committing other acts in connection with the same situation would have been possible (Sartre, 1943, p. 468).

As an atheist, Sartre did not connect human existence and their future to God, man for him is self-determined in obtaining whatever they wish to obtain. He affirmed that the nature of man cannot be sometimes free; he holistically and forever free or he is not free at all (Sartre, 1943, p. 441). He is of the opinion that freedom should not be restricted to voluntary acts rather volitions as passions are certain subjective character by which we try to achieve the ends posited by original freedom. Sartre strongly allied consciousness and choice as inseparable factors in connection to being-for-itself. And being-for-itself is a basic will-power a man has to determine and actualise his freedom in social context. As consciousness and choice serve as a factor to obtain freedom, Sartre backed his claim with Rene Descartes' popular maxim *cogito ergo sum*, thus, it is also to the 'cogito' that we appeal in order to determine freedom as the freedom which is ours, as a pure factual necessity; that is a contingent existence but one which I am not able not to experience (Sartre, 1943, 439).

Cause, motive, and end, were interchangeably used in Sartre as tripartite dictions to anchor the role of choice, consciousness and actualisation of freedom. Cause implies the reason or purpose behind an act that one intends to achieve or the ensemble of rational considerations which justifies the said act. While motive is considered as subjective fact, also the ensemble of the desire, and passion which inspires one to achieve particular objective. Being-in-the-world is not ordinary existence of man in the universe but living actively in connection to some performances both close and far. He further stated that the three key words that cause motive and end are the three indissoluble terms of the thrust of a free and living consciousness which project itself towards its possibilities and make itself defined by the possibilities. The direct and simple message of Sartre on freedom exposes man to radical jungle for freedom.

Insight on Existence Precedes Essence

Existence precedes essence is a central message of existentialist philosophy in context of Sartre. Man by nature is not born with predetermined origin, purpose or destiny but him alone chooses what he becomes. Whatever he becomes in the world, whether rich or poor, married or unmarried, educated or not educated depends on one's effort and creativity. Luck or miracle does not exist to assist man. Essence signifies the whatness, purpose and meaning of being in general. While existence represents the product or identity of the said essence. Sartre strongly maintained that man's origin and nature lack preparedness therefore man must strive to create essence for himself. In light of this, Jack Maden in his online

Philosophy Break (2023) cited Sartre saying (*Being and Nothingness*) there is no human nature, there is only a human condition. Having being "thrown" into the world, we constantly create and recreate ourselves as our lives unfold. We exist as first-conscious, first-person perspectives constantly imaging and reimagining who we are as we move through time. Sartre maintains that existence defines man's essence that is to say that the man's intelligence and creativities are manifestation of his existence. Once existence is in view freedom is guaranteed and progress assured.

Existentialism is a Humanism and Analogy of Paper Knife

This is a point where Sartre defended his claim that existence precedes essence and in converse posed a situation where essence precedes existence (vice versa). He likened his claim to a craftsman who manufactured “paper knife” and the maker of man. His subjective analysis is that human existence is the opposite of the existence of a manufactured product in like of “paper knife” whose essence precedes its existence because the manufacturer made it to complement particular purpose. This is an attempt to clarify that the manufacturer of the paper knife has a predetermined purpose and substance for the product while the maker of man did not have pre-determined purpose for the existence of man. That is why man should struggle to give essence to his existence.

Several allegations from communists and Christians were levelled against Sartre’s claims. Two from communists and two from Christians. 1. communists claimed that existentialism is action-averse, merely contemplative philosophy. 2. It remains caught in the pure subjectivity of Descartes. Meanwhile looking at existentialism on the meaning of individual identity paves way for ignoring the interconnections between individuals and their projects. For Christians; 1. “the suggestion that existentialism concentrates disproportionately on the negative aspects of life. 2. That its individualism would destroy any means by which people could condemn other’s actions.

Sartre held on the imperative that existentialism and humanism complement each other against the wishes of the critics. While his critics are of the view that existentialism is pessimistic, instead he reversed the case accusing them of being the main pessimists. He argued thus; the public uses the term as fashionable insult rather than actually understanding what it means also reminding the audience that existentialism is strictly intended for specialists and philosophers.

Effect of Freedom for Nigerian Society.

Freedom is the essence of humanism this portrays man as the architect of his own will-power. It is universal and central to human capacity building basically adopted to liberate man from social and mental constraints known as ‘bad faith’. The said bad faith is the major stereotype problem of Nigerian politicians orchestrated to truncate and tighten the chances of employment. This can easily lead to the failure of fulfilling campaign promises by politicians, executing and accomplishing government awarded projects. ‘Condemned to be free’ ‘authentic living’ and ‘radical choice’ making are reserved rights, liberty and avenue within the conscience of political leaders to choose and create employment to the masses. On this note, government and political leaders are charged to apply their radical freedom and choice to create essence to the existence of the people they represent. They are also condemned to create essence within the ambiance of government and governance which involves nation building, ultra-modern schools and hospitals, agricultural implementations, industries, employment, and security of lives and properties. Political leaders are not inherently good or bad rather the conscience and the kind of choice they make determine the outcome of their actions. Furthermore, the choice of principles, rules, policies, ethical choices and how their services are being rendered to the people define their political welfare to the people. Condemned to be free in the context is not restricted to leaders but interchangeable with the leaders and the citizens. By implication, the duo is free and condemned by choice and ‘leap of faith’ to reject corruption and embrace progressive mind, leaders who therefore prioritise their personal needs against the public are truly living in bad faith.

The Youth: the state of nation today such as government's failure to uphold and maintain the social contract agreement with the people has tremendously escalated into mass youth unemployment, fast-track-money making, like kidnapping, cybercrimes and looting of public funds, dependency on others, impatience, bad faith syndrome, lack of due process, lack of inner freedom, compromising impatience, and bad faith. These are parts of the problems in which this work is fundamentally addressing. Youthful age is the ripe time to reach out for capacity building such as, studies, creativity, money making and creation of broader future. The youth are charged to embrace a radical freedom as an access to self-realisation and self-creation because existence and freedom are free gifts of nature that both rich and poor share in common therefore no reason for being in bondage since freedom is free. Creativity is the inspiration that keep one's vision growing on daily basis. Individuals who have discovered their potentials have sidelined bad faith and have nothing to worry about unemployment and dependency on secondary sources like government, industry employment and others. Undertakers of authentic living and absolute freedom know the pros and cons of engaging in right and wrong businesses and therefore will not venture into doing wrong things. Existence precedes essence implies that a being already existing is indebted to creating meaning to its existence by working hard to becoming high profiled personality.

The effect of authenticity and bad faith demonstrate the state of dilemma challenging Nigerians especially the youth to reject bad faith, bondage, mental constraints, any foul means of making money and any activity that is detrimental to humans and the image of the country. Authentic living emphasizes that individuals have all it takes to actively achieve what they wish than blaming witches or some forces for hindering their success. Success is not a rocket science but a manifestation of opportunity meeting preparedness. Success has a workable procedure and element of physical contribution. Being educated requires schooling, being a doctor also requires studying medicine. The simple analogy is that one thing leads to the other for effective result.

Bad Faith in the Places of Worship: Faith without work is a paradigm of bad faith. And a faith without work portrays a situation where some groups of religious worshipers fix their faith and future to bigotry, superstition, and to what self-acclaimed clergymen always say. And the said worshippers have attached their beliefs and faith to whatever prophecy that is declared to them, just like what the Ghanaian man called Ebo Noah did. According to Ebo Noah, God was going to destroy the world with massive flood like the time of Noah precisely on 25th December 2025 and was instructed to build arks for safety of his followers. Many trooped in to Ghana to witness the event while others sold off their properties in that regards, eventually it did not come to fulfilment rather claiming that God postponed the mishap after several appeals. This is a clear attribute of bad faith that will likely ruin individuals' prospects and creativity in the name of waiting on prophecy and miracles to come. Bad faith in religion will likely truncate individual's dream if not spotted and dealt with. The effect of living authentic life does not come by accident but by choice and self-consciousness. Therefore, religious leaders must save the worshippers from engaging in bad faith by selecting and censoring their utterances to them as well expose them to social lives and activities to save them from living in bondage.

Many a time some clergymen caged worshippers, brainwashing them and putting fear into them so they can fall to any condition given to them especially at a trying time. On this note, magics are performed as miracles, prophecies are compromised in a manner that one's death will be pronounced with intention to exploit the poor individual. In many

occasions, worshippers are taught that paying of tithes and sowing of seeds alone are the criteria to becoming financially stable or that their reoccurring predicaments are as a result of not paying tithes and sewing of seeds. Meanwhile the spiritual leaders who preach that spiritual items protect individuals heavily surround themselves with armed security personnel. Prayer and work are duty bound responsibilities of man but must have time differences. Both are time-based and should not be negated because prayer goes with work as Latin maxim states ‘laborare est orare’ to work is to pray. Therefore, those who pray without work are living in bad faith and the way out is to choose authentic living and choice making.

The opposite of bad faith is good faith, and good faith is akin to radical choice making in Sartrean context. Worshippers are hereby charged not to be stagnant but dynamic with work after prayers and worship. Procrastination defines bad faith especially when situation requires urgency but not met due to indecisiveness.

Critique

The piece of cashphrase “man being condemned to be free” contains ingredients of critiqueable attributes. “Condemned to be free” issues license to blank order which may lead to consequential abuse of human right. Being condemned to be free breaks some limitations of human freedom. The context of the statement defines freedom as ‘absolute’ and limitless in nature and being absolute and limitless is detrimental to the peace of human right, because limitation of freedom guides and limits one from infringing on another’s rights.

If “condemned to be free” negates limitations of human right, it follows that man may freely use the freedom to bully or outshine the fellow. Absolute freedom is a weapon and threat to humanity. It stands tall with equivocation that Sartre gave a handover note of freedom to humanity with only “dos” without “don’ts, where then is a place of order and discipline? Man may be in the state of disarray for the search of freedom. While Sartre affirmed that seeking freedom is a matter of choice and individual race. Gabriel Marcel in contrast stressed that seeking freedom is not mere choice and individual affairs, rather the idea of freedom is more meaningful for “being” and “relation” than individual affair. More so objected that if we simply exercise our freedom through choice making we have no basis for judging the choices that others make (Gabriel,2024 para 2). More so emphasized that, authentic freedom involves acting significantly and participating in a shared human experience, rather than simply asserting one’s individual will. Man truly deserves freedom though not proper to utilise it without clause. Man is rather condemned to live with limitations of freedom than living on absolutism.

Simone critiqued Sartre of being too strict to acquiring freedom without sufficiently provided ethical tools to prevent oppression of the masses. She emphasized that while Sartre concentrates on freedom he failed to recognise the vitality of ‘power’ which is the basic force that may hinder the actions of individuals who are free in their consciousness. According to her, there is an element of disparity between power and freedom. While power is the ability to influence change in the society. Individuals enjoy freedom in consciousness, then the ability and chances to exercise the freedom becomes hindered by external forces. She further accused his concept of freedom as being too abstract and personal, notwithstanding, lacked merit as regards to ethical framework to address the main world suppression.

Existence precedes essence is another worrisome position Sartre posed to the human space. He is of the opinion that existence is primarily superior to essence. While essence is of secondary or prelude to existence. Juxtaposing the two, Sartre chose existence more valuable because he wanted to defend what he believed. As atheist and existentialist, he lacked the divine direction and sight to see things of the Spirit or affiliated between God and man. As materialist he is bound to see beyond material zone. Essence signifies “meaning” and “purpose” of a being. Before a being exists in the material world, the essence had been pre-defined by the maker. The manufacturer of biro must have pre-determined the usefulness of writing before manufacturing it. More so, before man and woman propose to marry each other they must have thought about procreation and companionship as the essence. Therefore, the Maker of man must have pre-determined their affairs in the world. In what way did existence precede essence? It is quite action-averse if considered that existence truly precedes essence in Sartre’s context.

Existence is the brainchild of essence. What ‘matter’ is to ‘form’ is what existence is to essence. Essence is existence’s DNA. Consider flower for instance, at times we see it and admire it because it is beautiful, little did we know that it is not the owner of the “beauty” until it withers. After withering the beauty lives it and reincarnates to another flower meaning that beauty (the essence) does not die but beautiful things do. Therefore, essence signifies the beauty that never dies but gives essence to existence. Any claim contrary to this is putting a cart before the horse. Where did Sartre and Heidegger sourced the claim that man was “thrown” into the world without pre-determined purpose? Even when the civil society confronted him that his claims were pessimistic and action-averse instead of making clarity he emphatically asserted that his claim is strictly intended for specialists and philosophers.

Essence is the “Matter” that gives existence “form”. If existence truly precedes essence, it follows that existence predetermines essence which is absurd. Before a child is born the essence as a replica of “matter” has predetermined the sex. Existence has no option than to accept the outcome of the essence. And the existence lacks the capacity to change the intrinsic nature that essence gave to an existing being. Existence therefore remains the product of essence. The emphasis that “man is condemned to be free” should be paraphrased as “man has the freedom to live freely”.

Evaluation and Conclusion

The role, position and pursuit of freedom in context discovered a lot of pros in gaining freedom and cons in lacking freedom for humanity. The research proved with convictions that freedom is the access to self-realisation and quiddity of man’s authentic life. Discoveries have it that the position of philosophical freedom succeeded in addressing volumes of common problems of individuals, government, and religion. The work successfully addressed the problems of bad faith in different social parastatals proffering solution and alternative to present and future society. Sartre ignited a motivational upsurge to the universal ensemble that nature did not have any pre-determined success to anybody unless they arise and conquer their constraints and facticity around them. This statement is a social liberation landmark to every individual who lives in bad faith.

The research found that self-freedom is not the only freedom that man requires but should be extended to political, social and religious dimensions so non should be living in isolation and dictation of others. The impression and imperative that nature did not have any pre-defined purpose and success for man is urgent call for urgent answer. Findings also have it that pursuit for freedom was outright homocentric and deistic. It is homocentric because all activities are restricted to man, deistic because neither God nor gods intervene into the affairs of man’s struggle to freedom and success. This posed a direct message that man should realise his capacity and make his way than shifting responsibilities and blames to any being.

By the virtue of existentialism, the world was screened as a total material structure where everyone struggles for their ends meet. For man to actualise his purpose, he must be free and being free is not coming freely unless by choice and struggle. Humans are regarded as microcosm that pilot the operating system of the macrocosm because nothing is more centralised in the cosmic order than human beings. The study more so revived and activated dormant minded ones into active existence by unveiling the curtain of bad faith to self-realisation.

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